

SECTION A: Introduction

Briefly introduce yourself.

Introduction to the parents

We would like to thank you for having accepted our invitation to discuss with you. You were invited because your child has participated in the “Be smart about your health” lessons. The purpose of those lessons was to help young people learn to think critically about “health actions” things that people do to care for their health or the health of others.

The purpose of this discussion is to explore with you as a parent some of the factors that might have affected what your children got out of these lessons and their ability to use what they learned. These factors could be related to the home environment, interaction with your child regarding what they learnt and anything else you think might be important.

We would like to know about things that might have contributed to good (effective) teaching or learning experiences for the students, but also about things that you felt were problematic.

There is no right or wrong answer.

The information you give us will help us to understand what students learned, whether they have been able to use what they learned, and how “the be smart about your health” lessons could be integrated in the curriculum and be scaled up country wide and elsewhere.

Please remember that whatever information we get from you will be kept confidential.

Tell parents how long the session will last (at least an hour).

Tell parents that:

- *We want to record the session so we can be sure of what you said.*
- *We will not attach names to the notes or recording.*

Ask if parents have any questions.

Start recording if given consent.

SECTION B: Focus group questions**Home Learning Environment**

1. Have you heard about the “Be smart about your health” lessons that your children attended this term?

Prompts:

- What have you heard?
- From whom?
- Have you talked about the lessons with your child?
 - If so, what did you discuss?

Notes

2. Did your child ever talk with you about their “homework”?

Prompts:

- If YES, what did you think about the homework?
- Did you help your child how with the homework?
- If so, how did you help your child?

Narrative summary, with quotes

3. Have you recently talked with your child about what people, or the radio or other media say about health – for example, things one can do to improve one’s health?

Narrative summary, with quotes

Intended and unintended effect

6a. Given what you know about the “Be smart about your health” lessons, how do you think your child benefitted from these lessons?

Prompts:

- Have you observed or experienced any of those benefits or advantages?
- **If yes:** Can you tell us about what you observed or experienced?

Narrative summary, with quotes

6b. Do you think there are any disadvantages of your child’s participation in the lessons?

Prompts:

- Have you observed or experienced any of those disadvantages?
- **If yes:** Can you tell us about what you observed or experienced?

Do not mention this but check the tendency to mention these below:

- Conflict between children and teachers
- *Distrust of health professionals*
- *Conflict due to undermining of religious beliefs*

Narrative summary, with quotes

7. Do you think what students learn would cause conflict between you and your child

Narrative summary, with quotes

Transfer

8. Did your child use anything they learned in the lessons at home/ with family/ when they are with friends? If so, please tell us about it.

Prompt:

-Has he/she taken something learned in the lessons and used it in a different subject or field?

Narrative summary, with quotes

9. Wrap-up

Is there anything else you would like to discuss?

Narrative summary, with quotes

Stop recording and thank them.